

SynSICRIS

Criteria set

**Evaluating the potential impact
of research projects**

Working paper

SynSICRIS Criteria-Set

Evaluating the potential impact of research projects

Status 08 / 2024

Authors: Wolf, Birge; Moser, Andrea; Kühn; David, Michaelis, Thorsten; Lange, Doris

SynSICRIS
Universität Kassel
Nordbahnhofstraße 1a
37213 Witzenhausen
Telefon: +49 5542-98 1536
Email: mail@synsicris.de
Email: birge.wolf@uni-kassel.de
Email: thorsten.michaelis@uni-kassel.de
<https://www.uni-kassel.de/forschung/synsicris/>

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

The Creative Commons Attribution license allows re-distribution and re-use of a licensed work on the condition that the creator is appropriately credited.

© SynSICRIS, Universität Kassel. Wolf, Birge; Moser, Andrea; Kühn; David, Michaelis, Thorsten; Lange, Doris

Table of contents

Context and Overview of the criteria set	4
Dimension: Scientific integrity	7
Dimension: Ethical integrity	7
Dimension: Gender equity	8
Dimension: Knowledge integration for the development of solutions	8
Dimension: Transfer activities.....	9
Dimension: Development of innovations and solutions	10
Dimension: Strengthening innovation capacity	10
Dimension: Reflection of the sustainability impact	11
Dimension: Estimation of sustainability impact	11

Context and Overview of the criteria set

Background

Research funding is increasingly aimed at ensuring that research and development contribute to overcoming social challenges. Research findings should lead to innovations or the implementation of solutions and changes and thus contribute to sustainable development.

Social impact is desirable, but can only be measured to a limited extent. Due to the open-ended nature of research and the complexity of innovation systems, impact can only be measured with a time lag and to a limited extent. In addition, the allocation to individual research projects and the fairness of the assessment with regard to the researchers is problematic.

This set of criteria therefore focusses on assessing potential impact. This provides timely results that can be used for steering processes in funding and programme evaluations as well as for optimisation processes. A fair assessment of researchers and projects can be carried out, which can then also be taken into account in the reputation.

Evaluation criteria for the diversity of research and development

The evaluation criteria we have developed are designed to take into account the diversity of different project types, innovations and funding programmes. The set of criteria therefore includes different ways in which research can be impactful.

Central to this is the concept of productive interactions between research and non-scientific stakeholders, which can take place directly and indirectly and are an indispensable prerequisite for the development of impacts. This approach was supplemented in terms of content and process-orientation by the discourse on responsible research and innovation and criteria from transdisciplinary research, innovation research, knowledge and technology transfer as well as sustainability assessment and technology assessment.

The criteria set covers nine dimensions that combine interactions, reflexivity, an assessment of outcomes and potential social impact. This enables an assessment of the potential impact of research projects in a transparent, standardised and well-founded manner.

Connection with the monitoring tool

The content of the criteria set and the SynSICRIS monitoring tool have been aligned. Data on interactions, reflection, outcomes and potential effects are recorded in the SynSICRIS tool during the project and are then available for the evaluation of the criteria by experts.

In principle, the criteria can also be used without the monitoring tool, but it cannot be guaranteed that all the necessary information will be available.

Figure 1 Dimensions of the Criteria-Set

How to use the criteria

All criteria are formulated in a way that allows for rating on a 5-point Likert scale, and the reviewing experts should be given the opportunity to provide a qualitative statement.

It is recommended that external experts from both the relevant scientific field of research and the practical/social field of action of the project assess the criteria. This combination of expertise is beneficial for ensuring comprehensive coverage of all aspects of the criteria.

In order to utilise the criteria in conjunction with the monitoring tool, each criterion is associated with one or more entities, where the relevant information can be located. For initial users, this can be combined with a path information, as illustrated in Figure 2 as an example.

Progress of applicability						
36	In terms of applicability or usability of the possible innovation, significant progress was made during the Project.	Does not apply	Rather does not apply	Partly/ partly	Rather applies	Applies completely
		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Notes, comments, Begründungen:						
Path: (SynSICRIS-Monitoring-Tool)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact pathway: Application (possibilities) - Application of a solution / change / innovation • Impact pathway: Application (possibilities) - Possible solution / change / innovation - (Please note all entries in this section, including any different versions) 				

Figure 2: Example, how to bring the criteria into a questionnaire.

Dimension: Scientific integrity

Scientific integrity		
1	Relevance	Context and relevance of the research question / project objective are .
2	Consideration of the current state of research	The current state of research has been comprehensively taken into account.
3	Methodology	The methodological approach was comprehensively disclosed.
4	Fulfillment of subject-specific requirements	The methods used correspond to the subject-specific requirements.
5	Reproducibility	The researchers have ensured reproduction and reuse of the data (including organisms, materials, software).
6	Completeness	The research results were completely described.
7	References	In publications, sources and references were fully indicated.
8	Transparency	The origin of all data, organisms, materials and software used was fully identified.

Dimension: Ethical integrity

Ethical integrity		
9	Adequate selection of ethical aspects	Relevant ethical aspects were reflected for the research project.
10	Early reflection	Ethical reflection took place at an early stage (application / project start).
11	Appropriate handling	Relevant ethical aspects are handled appropriately.
F1	Filter: Substantial ethical aspects	Were sensitive ethical aspects touched within the research project? (YES / NO)
12a	Detailed reflection	ONLY IF YES: Sensitive ethical aspects were reflected on in more detail during the course of the project.
13a	Consideration of different perspectives	ONLY IF YES: Different perspectives and the potential for socio-political conflict were taken into account when reflecting on sensitive ethical aspects.

Dimension: Gender equity

Gender equity		
15	Early reflection	Aspects of gender equality were reflected at an early stage (application / project start).
14	Consideration of gender equality	All aspects of gender equality were appropriately taken into account in the project.
16	Gender equality actions	The research project implemented appropriate actions to promote equality among employees.
17	Balance of gender relations	The gender ratio in the project was balanced with regard to the personnel possibilities of the subject area.

Dimension: Knowledge integration for the development of solutions

Knowledge integration for the development of solutions		
18	Integration of relevant disciplines	The project integrated knowledge from disciplines / research fields relevant to the problem solution.
19	Timely collaboration (research field)	Interactions with various disciplines / research fields, took place early and continuously.
20	Format of interactions (research field)	The format of interactions in the project was suitable for integrating knowledge from different disciplines/research fields.
21	Integration of relevant fields of action	In the project, knowledge from the fields of action relevant to problem solving was integrated.
22	Early collaboration (field of action)	Interactions were held with the relevant fields of action at an early stage and on a continuous basis.
23	Format of interactions (field of action)	The format of interactions in the project was suitable for integrating knowledge from the specific field of action.
24	Results include knowledge integration	Knowledge integration (research field and field of action) is clearly evident in the results.
F2	Filter: Adaptivity	Were there any significant changes in the general conditions or unexpected intermediate results and information situations during the course of the project? (Yes/No)
25	Adaptivity	ONLY IF YES: In the project, the work was flexibly adapted to changing general conditions and information situations.

Dimension: Transfer activities

Transfer activities		
F3	Filter: property rights (YES / NO)	Did the project apply for an industrial property right (patent, utility model)?
26a	Property rights strategy	If Yes: The researchers have plausibly demonstrated that property right applications are a suitable strategy to contribute to a later use of the results.
27a	Open access (beyond property right)	If Yes: All results that are not affected by property rights have been made available permanently, free of charge and without access barriers.
28a	Target group orientation (beyond property right)	If Yes: The research work and results not affected by the property right were prepared in a target group-oriented manner.
29a	Multipliers (beyond property right)	If Yes: Suitable multipliers were identified and appropriately involved to contribute to the dissemination of results not affected by patent rights.
27b	Open access	If No: All results were made publicly available free of charge and without access barriers.
28b	Target group orientation	If No: The research work and results were processed in a target group-oriented manner.
29b	Multipliers / Intermediaries / Key Stakeholder	If No: Suitable multipliers were identified and appropriately involved to contribute to dissemination of the results.

Dimension: Development of innovations and solutions

Development of innovations and solutions		
30	Degree of novelty	Potentials and deficits were plausibly presented with regard to the degree of novelty of the possible innovation.
31	Efficiency	Potentials and deficits of the efficiency of the possible innovation were plausibly presented (also in comparison to previous practices and approaches).
32	Practicability and connectivity	Potentials and deficits were plausibly presented with regard to the practicability and connectivity of the possible innovation.
33	Requirements	The necessary conditions for the application of the possible innovation were plausibly described.
34	Establishment potential	The prospects for establishment/dissemination/transfer of the possible innovation was plausibly presented.
35	Identification of deficits	In the research project, concrete measures were implemented to identify deficits in the applicability and lacks in the benefits of the possible innovation.
36	Progress of applicability	In terms of applicability or usability of the possible innovation, significant progress was made during the Project.
F4	Filter: insufficient applicability	Was it determined during the course of the project that application of the results is not possible or that the potential innovation is not suitable for application or has deficiencies in utility?
37a	Communication of insufficient applicability	If Yes: Insufficient applicability was clearly communicated by the researchers.
38	Added value for users	The possible innovation indicates a clear added value for the users.
39	Innovation development	The project's work was clearly aimed at contributing to innovation development.

Dimension: Strengthening innovation capacity

Strengthening innovation capacity		
40	Competence promoting interactions	The interactions in the project were well suited to increase the competence of the involved actors to participate in innovation processes.
41	Cross-organizational exchange	The competencies of research and application-oriented actors were brought together across organizations to promote innovation processes.
42	Open innovation networks	The project has contributed to open networks in which the development of further innovations is sought.

Dimension: Reflection of the sustainability impact

Reflection of the sustainability impact		
43	Early reflection	The reflection of possible positive and negative impacts of the possible innovation, took place at an early stage (at the time of application / project start).
44	System orientation	It is clear that potential positive and negative impacts were reflected in a system-oriented manner.
45	Reflection of negative side effects	Potential negative side effects of the possible innovation were reflected and uncertainties in the state of research were considered.
46	Reflection of positive impacts	Potential positive impacts of the possible innovation were plausibly presented, including a differentiation between provable and hypothetical effects.
47	Transdisciplinary impact assessment	In order to assess the effects or side effects of the possible innovation, relevant research fields / disciplines and actors from the field of action were included.

Dimension: Estimation of sustainability impact

Estimation of sustainability impact		
48	Risk assessment (sustainability)	There is a clear risk of negative side effects from the use of the possible innovation.
49	Assessment of potential impact (sustainability)	The possible innovation has the potential to achieve strong positive impacts in its area of application.
50	Reducing negative side effects	Work has been done to reduce the negative side effects of the potential innovation.
51	Optimization of positive effects	Work has been done to maximise the positive impacts of the potential innovation.
52	Reduction of trade-offs	Work has been done to reduce trade-offs between sustainability impacts.